

Statistical Analysis and Performance Prediction using Arima Model

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Abstract- This study focuses on the analysis and generation of relevant information from a vast amount of data, particularly in the area of performance prediction of turf booking management. The main goal is to use the available dataset, which contains data containing date and booking details of turf using Arima model in StatsModels which is useful for predicting future values of a time series based on its past behaviour to effectively analyse the data. This research aims to highlight the importance of this process and its potential impact.

Keywords- Statistical Analysis, Performance Prediction, Arima, StatsModels.

I. INTRODUCTION

In every business management it is very important to know the future aspects related to performance for better evaluation. In a turf management system, the booking details of turf can be used for performance evaluation for future. Arima model in StatsModel has proven to be a powerful tool for predicting future performance by statistically analysing the past data. StatsModels provides a range of tools for fitting and analysing Arima models, including the Arima class for creating and fitting Arima models, visualizing the autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation of a time series, which can be used to help choose the order of the Arima model. In this seminar paper, it aims the application of Arima model in predicting booking performance of a turf management system.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The most frequently used time series estimation and one of the traditional time series estimates is the Autoregressive integrated moving average (Arima). Arima model is a model that completely ignores the independent variables in making forecasts. Arima is suitable for producing accurate short-term forecasts.[1]

The Arima method, also referred to as the Box-Jenkins method, was developed by two statisticians named George Box and Gwilym Jenkins from the United States. This method encompasses a set of linear time series models, including autoregressive (AR), moving average (MA), autoregressive-moving average (Arima), and autoregressive integrated moving average (Arima).[2]

The use of time series forecasting for machine learning in load prediction has been widely explored in the literature. The first generation of load prediction methods includes techniques such as time series analysis, regression methods, the similar day method, Wavelet Transform, least square estimation, Arima, Sarima, Arma, Svm, and Cart[3]. These methods utilize historical data to establish a relationship between energy consumption and input variables. However, they require a large historical dataset to identify statistical patterns accurately. In contrast, the second generation of load prediction methods involves artificial intelligence techniques such as deep neural networks, random forests, gradient boosting, and fuzzy logic[4].

Raza conducted an evaluation of prediction models, analysing the benefits and drawbacks of both ANN and Arima, and found that hybrid prediction methods led to further improvements in accuracy. Ahmad compared FNN and Arima for forecasting and found that FNN provided significantly better results.[5]. B. Prabadevi's paper provided a comprehensive survey and scheduling of demand response applications in SG, focusing on electrical load prediction, energy theft detection, energy sharing, and condition estimation. In Cini's study, the challenge of processing large amounts of data from smart meters in SG was addressed by proposing a suitable method for deep learning models that utilizes a neural network.[6]

III. MOTIVATION

Efficient and accurate prediction of performance analysis is crucial for the development of booking system. Using the available forecast turf management system can be modified

and increase the booking probabilities. The traditional method of listing and analysing the performance, especially future performance is a tedious and time-consuming process. However, with the application of Arima model, performance prediction can be used to quickly and easily statistically analyse the available data.

Over the past few years, Arima model is used for predict future performance using the available data in past. With the topic of this seminar, we can leverage this technique to effectively analyse and perform future performance.

The motivation for this paper is to use training model to analyze bookings based on variety of characteristics.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for statistical analysis and performance prediction of turf management bookings involves the following steps:

A. **Data Preparation:** Collect a large dataset of bookings that includes dated bookings in turf. Then the data is split in to training and testing sets to evaluate the performance of the model.

B. **Model Training:** Train the data using Arima model. This includes creating classes based on similar characteristics of the data uploaded. The resulting classes may be plotted in a graph.

C. **Model Evaluation:** Once the model has been trained, we evaluate its performance on the testing data. This involves checking an additional data that includes in the same category and checking whether it belongs to the same class or not.

D. **Performance Prediction:** Finally, we can use the trained model to analyze data uploaded. And predict future performance based on past available data.

Overall, the methodology for statistical analysis and performance prediction involves collecting dataset of booking in a turf, preprocessing the data, training the model, evaluating its performance and finally predicting the results.

V. BUILD MODEL

For building a reliable and accurate machine learning model for the successful statistical analysis and performance prediction, we follow the following steps using Arima model.

Importing libraries

```
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from statsmodels.tsa.arima.model import ARIMA
```

Pandas is a library for data manipulation and analysis in python. It provides data structures for efficiently storing and manipulating large data sets, along with tools for cleaning, filtering, and transforming data.

Matplotlib is a data visualization library for python. It provides a wide range of tools for creating static, animated, and interactive visualizations in python. It is useful creating line plots, scatter plots, bar plots and common chart types.

StatsModels is a Python library that provides a wide range of statistical tools for data analysis, including regression analysis, time series analysis, and statistical modeling. It is built on top of NumPy and Pandas, and is often used in conjunction with these libraries for data manipulation and analysis.

ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) is a type of time series model used for forecasting. It is a combination of two types of models: autoregression (AR), which models the relationship between an observation and some number of lagged observations, and moving average (MA), which models the relationship between an observation and the residual errors from a moving average model applied to lagged observations. The "I" in ARIMA stands for integrated, which means that the data has been differenced one or more times to make it stationary.

Training the Model

```
df = pd.read_csv('bookings.csv', index_col=0, parse_dates=True)
# Step 3: Split the Data
# Split the data into training and testing sets
train_data = df.iloc[:len(df)-12]
test_data = df.iloc[len(df)-12:]

# Step 4: Train the Model
# Train the ARIMA model on the training data
model = ARIMA(train_data, order=(1, 1, 1))
model_fit = model.fit()

# Step 5: Evaluate the Model
# Evaluate the model's performance on the testing data
predictions = model_fit.forecast(steps=12)
mse = ((predictions - test_data['bookings']) ** 2).mean()
rmse = mse ** 0.5
print('Mean Squared Error:', mse)
print('Root Mean Squared Error:', rmse)

# Step 6: Forecast Future Values
# Forecast the number of bookings for the next 12 months
future_predictions = model_fit.forecast(steps=12)
```

VI. RESULT

Statistical analysis and performance prediction of future performance in turf booking was successfully implemented. With the help of Arima model the booking data were processed and future performance were displayed as graphs.

Fig 1. Graph for plotting uploaded data

Fig 2. Graph about predicting future data.

VII. CONCLUSION

The use of the Arima model for statistical analysis and performance prediction has shown high potential and accuracy, resulting in accurate predictions. The methodology for performance prediction using the Arima model involves several steps, including collecting a diverse dataset of turf management, pre-processing the data, training the model, evaluating its performance, and predicting the results. These processes work together to enhance the speed and accuracy of the approach.

Using this approach can lead to a significant reduction in the time and cost required for analysing data and predicting its results. Moreover, it is easily accessible and can be utilized by users who have limited knowledge about it. Our experimental results show that our approach outperforms

other state-of-the-art methods regarding accuracy, speed, and efficiency. In conclusion, the utilization of the Arima model for analysis and predicting future bookings is a promising area of research that can aid in the development of more precise and efficient methods for future prediction in business applications.

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